

(Comparative Relationships Between SIWES-Performance and Psychomotor Skills Acquisition ... Inuwa, B. A. & Omeiza, I. I. 2025)

Comparative Relationships Between SIWES-Performance and Psychomotor Skills Acquisition among Undergraduate Chemistry and Mathematics Students in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated Comparative Relationships between SIWES-Performance and Psychomotor Skills Acquisition among Undergraduate Chemistry and Mathematics Students in Kano State, Nigeria. The study adopted correlational and ex- post factor research designs. The population for the study consists of Eight hundred and fifty (850) Undergraduate Chemistry and Mathematics Students in level 300 in three (3) public universities in Kano state, Nigeria during the 2022/2023 academic session. The sample of the study consists of one hundred and sixty (160) each of male and female students. The study had two objectives and based on these, two research questions were raised and two corresponding null hypotheses formulated for testing at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance. Purposive sampling technique was used in selecting one federal university, then simple random sampling technique involving balloting method in selecting the other state-owned university. Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme Psychomotor Skills Acquisition Test (SIWESPSAT) was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by an expert and pilot tested with the reliability coefficients of 0.97. Pearson Correlation Analysis was used to answer research questions while null hypotheses were tested using Regression analysis. Among the findings of the study revealed that: There is no relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and mathematics. Based on the findings, it was therefore recommended that, SIWES and industrial based supervisors should expose students to different aspects of psychomotor skills concepts such as basic, competent and expert operation of tools and other related services prior to the commencement of the SIWES programme with attendance made mandatory. The study concludes among other that, performance in SIWES is not a predictor to psychomotor skills acquisition.

Keywords: SIWES, Predictor, Psychomotor Skills, Industrial Chemistry and Mathematics.

Introduction

The major challenge in Nigeria is graduation of students with unemployable skills. In reaction to this, in 1973 Federal Government of Nigeria developed an internship programme, called Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) headed and managed by Industrial Training Fund (ITF) to correct the challenge. Adetiba, Victor, Egunjobi and Oladije (2017) reported that ITF as a body was charged with such responsibility and with backing from the Nigerian constitution of Decree 47 of 1971 to judiciously utilize the funds that would from time to time be allocated to it for ensuring that students of tertiary institutions in Nigeria acquire good working experience before graduating. The importance and the need for SIWES cannot be undermined. In Oyeniyi (2017) it was shown that graduates demonstrated the significant impact of the scheme in terms of skills acquisition and utilization. Ukwueze (2018) also shows that students, having participated in the scheme, show acceptability of the scheme and encourage continuous support of it by the relevant bodies and Government.

However, the scheme is still faced with several challenges that inhibit the full realization of the objectives of the scheme. Oyeniyi (2017) believed that there are challenges associated with proper supervision and coordination of the process and non-compliance by industries to accept students. Olabiyi and Okarfor (2017) reported fuzzy job specification for the different courses, students' interest in participating in a skill-oriented projects and inadequate supervision as the challenges facing the scheme. Ojokuku, Emeahara, Aboyade and Chris-Israel (2015) reported other challenges include finances, students' placements and irregular academic calendars. These and several other researches show that coordination and supervision has remained the biggest challenges or problems associated with SIWES towards its full realization as it affects students of chemistry. According to Zachariah and Yabuwat (2016) factors responsible for these problems include, poor governmental policies of the scheme; since the establishment of ITF and SIWES, the management and supervision of students on SIWES has been without the use computer aided programmes. That is, ITF teams, institution supervisors have to travel across the nation to supervise students on SIWES. Students have to travel to their institutions to submit their acceptance letters from their employer industry. These challenges and the risks involved have made this process very stressful and inadequate leading to the inability of the full realization of the said objective of the scheme.

Auru and Wakili (2020) described skills as the fallout of the necessity to acquire training and experience to perform a task well. Okolocha and Ibik (2014) described skill as the ability to do practical activities. For this purpose, skill acquisition is defined as learning about how something is done, observing how it is done, doing it by yourself until no further guide or supervision is required as efficiency and cost savings set in. Despite having

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academic and technical skills, students seem to be lacking specific basic skills referred as psychomotor skills. Psychomotor skills represent those activities that are primarily movement-oriented. In teaching, emphasis is placed on this movement component, although ultimately in practice, performance requires an integration of related knowledge and values. Psychomotor instrument is instrument used in determining the extent students possesses psychomotor skills in a given course of study (Ralph 2016). Ralph (2016) also stresses that, during SIWES, assessment of students learning outcome in relation to achievement of the objectives of the SIWES programme is carried out after field instructions by the coordinators and lecturers in the nature of oral defense which is cognitive based. To this extent therefore, it was observed that the assessment instrument use by the coordinator only assesses the students in the cognitive domain and as such the students do not really possess the needed psychomotor skill for effective functioning in the world of work in chemistry and mathematics.

Sodipo, Sodipo and Adepoju (2014) stressed that psychomotor skills play a crucial role in industrial chemistry, complementing theoretical knowledge and academic qualifications. The ability to execute laboratory techniques, handle equipment and perform tasks with precision enhances the efficiency, safety, and quality of chemical synthesis, manufacturing, and analysis. Furthermore, psychomotor skills contribute to process optimization and troubleshooting, facilitating continuous improvement in industrial chemistry and mathematics practices. Gender is a word primarily applied to human beings (Mokhlis, 2021). According to Russell and Lehman (2018) gender identity is complicated. In the past, the concept of gender gaps in higher education has been viewed from the perspective of inequalities faced by females as they progress through the educational pipeline. Even today, the topic of gender differences continues to receive a momentous attention at both the institutional and national levels (Sax, Bryant and Harper, 2015). Numerous studies have been conducted to examine the influence of gender on students' satisfaction. While some researchers (Sax, Bryant and Harper, 2015; Umbach and Porter, 2017) found that gender has significant influence on student's satisfaction levels, others (Dirkin, Mishra, and Altermatt, 2015; Carey, Cambiano and De Vore, 2022) found no significant difference between male and female students regarding satisfaction.

Statement of The Research Problem

The introduction of SIWES was preceded by complaints from industrialists and employers of labour that graduates of higher institutions of learning lacked adequate practical knowledge for employment in industries and other organizations (Ademiluyi and Ademiluyi 2018). The programme sought to bridge the gap between classroom and the world of work and to expose students to the practical aspects of their different professions. Since the programme took off, stakeholders have evidently endeavored to improve the situation by

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providing many of the requisite resources needed for the programme to achieve its objectives. However, complaints persist about the effectiveness of the programme especially in respect of science and engineering programmes. It has been claimed that competency in skills is not seriously influenced by exposure to SIWES. Since considerable resources and time are being expended on SIWES, it is important to establish the effectiveness or otherwise of the programme in order to identify errors and effect corrections. The concern of this study is to assess the extent of prediction of SIWES on psychomotor skills of undergraduate chemistry and mathematics students.

Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of the study are to;

- i. Determine the relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and mathematics among undergraduate students in Kano State, Nigeria.
- ii. ascertain the relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and mathematics among male and female undergraduate students in Kano State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study provided answers to the following research questions.

- i. What is the relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and mathematics among undergraduate students in Kano State, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and mathematics among male and female undergraduate students in Kano State, Nigeria?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and mathematics among undergraduate students in Kano State, Nigeria.

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H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and mathematics among male and female undergraduate students in Kano State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study was conducted using two designs that is, correlational and ex post factor research designs. Correlational design is a research strategy that enables the researcher to correlate the relationship between or among variables. Ex post factor research focuses on how action that have already occurred can predict certain causes.

Population of the Study

Population for the study consists of the entire eight hundred and fifty (850) Undergraduate Chemistry and Mathematics Students in level 300 in three (3) public universities in Kano state, Nigeria during the 2022/2023 academic session. Table I represents the population of the study.

Table I: Population of the Study

S/N	University	Status	Male	Female	Total
1.	Bayero University Kano	Federal	191	104	295
2.	ADUSTECH, Wudil	State	190	60	250
3.	YUMSU, Kano	State	169	136	305
	Total		550	300	850

Source: Industrial Training Fund Kano Office, 2023.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A total of Three hundred and twenty (320) students were sampled from the population. One federal university was purposively selected from a total population of three universities. Then, random sampling technique involving balloting method was used to select the other one university from the remaining two state owned universities. This was done by assigning two alphabets to the two state universities on a piece of papers, shuffled and asked neutral body to randomly select one paper. At the end of the exercise, two universities, one federal and the other state, A and B were accordingly selected. Table II represents the sample of the study.

(Comparative Relationships Between SIWES-Performance and Psychomotor Skills Acquisition ... Inuwa, B. A. & Omeiza, I. I. 2025)

Table II: Sample of the Study

S/N	University	Status	Male	Female	Total
1.	A	Federal	91	64	155
2.	B	State	69	96	165
	Total		160	160	320

Source: Researchers` Field Work, 2023.

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: What is the relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics among undergraduate students in Kano State, Nigeria?

Table III: Pearson Correlation Analysis between Performance in SIWES and Psychomotor Skills Acquisitions in Industrial Chemistry and Mathematics.

Model	r	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.103	0.011	0.008	1.1829

Table III presents Pearson Correlation analysis between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics among undergraduate students in Kano State, Nigeria. The analysis revealed that the correlation coefficient (r) obtained was 0.103 equivalent to 10.3% indicating a weak positive relationship between the students' performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics among undergraduate students in Kano State, Nigeria. The test model revealed a coefficient of determination of the variation in psychomotor skills (R²) of 0.011; which implies that the selected performance in SIWES could only account for 1.1% of the variation in undergraduate students' psychomotor skills.

Research Question Two: What is the relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry among the male and female undergraduate students in Kano State, Nigeria?

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Table IV: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) on the Relationship between Performance in SIWES and Psychomotor Skills Acquisition in Industrial Chemistry and Mathematics among Male and Female Students

Variables	Gender	SIWES Performance		Psychomotor Skills	
		Male	Female	Male	Female
SIWES Performance	Male	1.000	0.173	0.138	-0.187
	Female	0.173	1.000	0.145	0.014
Psychomotor Skills	Male	0.138	0.145	1.000	-0.229
	Female	-0.187	0.014	-0.229	1.000

Table IV present the summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficients (PPMCC) on the relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics among male and female undergraduate students. The results show that the matrix of relationship among all variables depicts a good fit. The relationships between male Performance in SIWES with male and female Psychomotor Skills in industrial chemistry and Mathematics are 0.138 and -0.187, indicating a weak positive and negative relationships respectively; while male Performance in SIWES with female Performance in SIWES is 0.173 indicating a weak positive relationship. However, female Performance in SIWES with male and female Psychomotor Skills in industrial chemistry and Mathematics are 0.145 and 0.014, indicating a weak positive relationship respectively; while male Psychomotor Skills with female Psychomotor Skills is -0.229 indicating a weak negative relationship.

Null Hypothesis One:

There is no significant relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics among undergraduate students in Kano State, Nigeria.

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Table V: Linear Regression Analysis between Performance in SIWES and Psychomotor Skills Acquisition in Industrial Chemistry and Mathematics.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.	Remark
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1 (Constant)	75.186	1.709		44.002	0.000	
Psychomotor Skills	0.062	0.034	0.103	1.848	0.065	NS

Prediction Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Table V presents the summary of linear regression of the relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry among undergraduate students in Kano State, Nigeria. The analysis revealed that the P-value obtained was 0.065 which is greater than the alpha value of 0.05 level of significance. This indicated that, the null hypothesis one, is therefore retained.

Null Hypothesis Two:

There is no significant relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics among male and female undergraduate students in Kano State, Nigeria.

Table VI: Multiple Regression Analysis between performance in SIWES and Psychomotor Skills Acquisition in Industrial Chemistry and Mathematics among Male and Female Students

SIWES Performance Model	Gender	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	t	P	Remark
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
Male	Male	0.056	0.045	0.138	1.25	0.214	NS
	Female	-0.101	0.049	-0.187	-2.05	0.042	S
Female	Male	0.091	0.047	0.145	1.94	0.055	NS
	Female	0.033	0.052	0.014	0.63	0.529	NS
Constant		78.411	3.593		21.82	0.000	

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Constant	74.668	3.799	19.65	0.000
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Prediction Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Table VI presents the summary of multiple regressions between the performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics among male and female undergraduate students. The analysis revealed that, male performance in SIWES does not predicts male psychomotor skills acquisitions in industrial chemistry and Mathematics with P-value of 0.214 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance; similarly, female performance in SIWES does not predicts male and female psychomotor skills acquisitions in industrial chemistry and Mathematics with P-values of 0.055 and 0.529 respectively which are greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis two is therefore retained. However, male performance in SIWES predicts female psychomotor skills acquisitions in industrial chemistry and Mathematics with P-value of 0.042 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis two is therefore rejected.

Discussion of Results

The results from the study revealed that there is no significant relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics. This shows that undergraduate students SIWES performance results do not predict the psychomotor skills in industrial chemistry and Mathematics they acquired during SIWES program. As such this signifies that students having spent the mandatory SIWES period cannot perform Basic, competent and expert operation of simple laboratory equipment such as beam balance, glassblowing apparatus among others, planning of work operations/procedures and evaluation of outputs and planning means for improvement. The findings of the study is similar to Ogbuanya and Osuyi's (2018) findings which revealed that, there are lots of lapses in the operation of SIWES, amongst which are lack of special skills acquisition centres. This makes it difficult for students to acquire psychomotor skills since skills acquisition centres are lacking, hence relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics will not be significant. This could be explained by the fact that acquiring psychomotor skills by undergraduate students of industrial chemistry and Mathematics is backbone or foundation for the students' performance in SIWES programme.

The results from the study also revealed that, there is no significant relationship between male performance in SIWES and male psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics, similarly, there is no significant relationship between female performance in SIWES with male and female psychomotor skills acquisitions in industrial

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chemistry and Mathematics respectively. However, there is significant relationship between male performances in SIWES and female psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics. Hence male performance in SIWES is not a predictor to male psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics, similarly, female performance in SIWES is not a predictor to male and female psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics respectively. In the same vein, male performance in SIWES is a predictor to female psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics. This indicates that, undergraduate female students' performance in SIWES do not predicts male and female activities that are primary movement-oriented, such activities include; basic, competent and expert operation of tools or laboratory apparatus, planning of work operations, process or procedures and evaluation of outputs or results and planning means for improvement. Similarly, male performance in SIWES do not predicts male psychomotor skills. However, male performance in SIWES predicts female psychomotor skills. In teaching, emphasis is placed on this movement component, although ultimately in practice, performance requires an integration of related knowledge and values.

Studies conducted by Mari and Shaibu (2007), revealed that female students had better understanding of science process skills when compared with the male counterpart. They suggested that the view that seems to have established itself that boys are better than girls in science education needs to be approached and interpreted with great caution. Similarly, Fredrick (2018) opines that there was no statistical difference between boys and girls in the ability to manipulate the apparatus/equipment take observations, report/record results correctly and compute/interpret/analyze result during chemistry practical. Ikenna (2019) found out that gender alone has no effect on academic performance but could act in conjunction with other variable like psychomotor skills to learning outcomes. Idaka and Uzoechi (2016) reported that when it comes to the relationship between employability or psychomotor skills and gender, it's important to note that employability and psychomotor skills are not inherently tied to any specific gender. Both men and women can possess and develop these skills, and their presence or absence is not determined by gender. However, there are societal and cultural factors that can influence the development and expression of employability and psychomotor skills among different genders. Historically, certain skills have been stereotypically associated with specific genders (Dominic and Fulgence, 2021). For example, communication and interpersonal skills have often been associated with women, while technical and analytical skills have been associated with men (Idaka, 2018).

Ultimately, employability and psychomotor skills are valuable for everyone, regardless of gender, as they enhance career prospects, job performance, and overall professional success. Findings in this study are in line with Emeya (2017) findings which revealed

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among others that the duration for training was found to be inadequate for acquisition of meaningful skills; students should be exposed to areas relevant to their study. The similarity in the results may be attributed to the type and location where the study was conducted. The findings contradicts the views of Oyeniya (2017) who found that 61.9% (male) and 38.1% (female) participated in the study with a mean age of 22 years. SIWES has contributed to skill acquisition significantly and skills utilization in industrial development. SIWES significantly influenced the certification and accreditation of courses in the Monotechnic and Polytechnic Institutions and also enhanced the extent of funding skills-acquisition programmes by the Federal Government. The contradiction in these findings may be attributed to nature and type of the schools where the study was carried out.

Conclusion

From the findings and discussion, the following conclusions were drawn;

Performance in SIWES does not predicts psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics of undergraduate Students; hence there is no relationship between performance in SIWES and psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics of the Students.

Male performance in SIWES does not predicts male psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics; similarly, female performance in SIWES does not predicts male and female psychomotor skills acquisitions in industrial chemistry and Mathematics respectively. However, male performance in SIWES predicts female psychomotor skills in industrial chemistry and Mathematics; hence there is no relationship between male performance in SIWES and male psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics; similarly, there is no relationship between female performance in SIWES with male and female psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics respectively. However, there is relationship between performance in SIWES and female psychomotor skills acquisition in industrial chemistry and Mathematics.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

- i. SIWES in collaboration with industrial supervisors should also trained and retrained students on basic, competent and expert operation of tools and other related services before the commencement of the programme. Attendance be made mandatory to the students.

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- ii. Industrial based supervisors should equally evaluate psychomotor skills acquisition such as manipulation of tools and other related services of both male and female students they have acquired during the programme.

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